

Paper 1

Employability Skills Management: Developing a Conceptual Model

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Abstract

To remain competitive in a technology driven globalised business environment, and pursue sustainable development goals, Companies today are demanding a higher degree of professionalism, emotional maturity, industry domain knowledge, and techno-functional competencies from the new breed of graduating students, engineers and value chain managers.

In context of higher education, to address these challenges, University Industry Collaboration is emerging a key growth area towards professional skill development efforts of graduating students. The genesis of this concept paper comes out from the need of strengthening Industry Academia Interface [I.A.I.], in context of academic value addition and value integration as mutually collaborative engagements, which would inadvertently supplement conventional classroom learning of traditional education formats.

To infuse a fresh perspective of looking at various competitive skills desired by the employers, in the categories of hard and soft skills, and with a blend of basic and advanced life skills, this conceptual paper attempts to illustrate a fresh re-look for managing the graduate employability skills traits.

This paper contains the concept proposal, structure, synthesis and graphical representation of the Employability Skills Management Quotient (ESMQ) model, from various organizational frames of references. It is believed that the proposed ESMQ Model would assist in designing varying levels of training interventions, through Accelerated Learning Programs (ALPs) that would distinctly enhance the overall employability of graduating students; consequently making them ready for speedy absorption in Businesses and Industry.

Keywords: Basic Skills, Advance Skills, Vocational skills, Hard skills, Soft Skills, Technical Skills, Higher education, Graduate employability, Skill Training, Skill Quotient,

1. INTRODUCTION:

In the 21st century macro-environment, Businesses and Industry are facing ever intensifying competition in terms of rapidly globalizing economies, e-commerce, disruptive technologies and

ecological challenges. The micro dynamics of accelerated globalization is posing a sustainability challenge onto business organizations worldwide, both in terms of improving their overall competitiveness and for sustaining future growth. [1-3]

Moreover in a much more complex, multicultural and diverse organization fabric today, organizations continue to face the competitive pressures for developing innovative technology, contemporary management tools, as well as improving Human Resource Productivity.

Furthermore the swiftness of skill set disruption, unprecedented rate of change in transforming functional or occupational employability skills and the degree of productive professionalism sought from the many; demands a contemporary relook towards development of newer skills, competencies and employability skill improvement across organizations and institutions worldwide, especially in developing and emerging countries [4-10].

Eventually this may need to dwell upon redefining the traditional academic value proposition of professional education in the 21st century, in order to keep abreast with the changing global business scenario. Over the past decade, several concerns on a pressing need for skill development in functional as well as vocational domains on both side of the academia vs. industry supply chain, highlighting the widening gap in employment vs. employability skills, technical skill shortages as well as inconsistencies in core work related skills have been published. Employability skill improvement and management is being actively debated in the academic domain and across governments, businesses, industries and training organizations in several forums. [11-41]

It is in this context an effort is made to systematize and structure a contemporary collaborative engagement [12, 18], between Academia and Industry i.e. Universities Industry Collaboration in this context. An illustration of Collaborative engagement for Organization Development and Employability (C.O.D.E.) for value addition and value integration, between Industry and Academia, and vice versa, is proposed in this paper as a prelude to Employability Skill Management Quotient [E.S.M.Q.]. [41-46]

Subsequently, a perspective of the conceptual model is illustrated both in tabular and graphical format, to describe the Employability Skill Management Quotient (ESMQ) that would include the four sub groupings or categories named as Intellectual Skills Management Quotient (ISMQ), Technical Skills Management Quotient (TSMQ), Professional/Functional Skills Management Quotient (PSMQ) and Socio-Cultural Skills Management Quotient (SCSMQ). Within each category, various subsets of skill trait elements have been renamed manually, so as to define and develop a perspective of an Employability Skill Management Quotient (ESMQ) i.e. to describe a non empirical summation to represent $ESMQ = \sum ISMQ_n + \sum TSMQ_n + \sum PSMQ_n + \sum SCSMQ_n$

2. RESEARCH OBJECTIVE:

The objective of this paper is to build a conceptual framework of a suitable employability skills management quotient model from an academic and industry perspective. The genesis of this concept paper comes out from the need of strengthening Industry Academia Interface [I.A.I.], in context of academic value addition and value integration for a mutually beneficial relationship between academia and industry and that is named as Collaborative Engagement for Organizational Development and Employability (C.O.D.E.)

To develop Employability Skill Management Quotient (ESMQ), with its four sub-set Skill categories that would assist in designing appropriate training interventions through Accelerated Learning Programs (ALPs) beyond routine, for improving the professional development of prospective and current employees in an organization.

3. LITERATURE REVIEW

Graduate employability and skill enhancement effort is subject of active research from many years, with in-depth analysis and extensive deliberations on the terminology, meaning, perspective descriptions, composition, correlations, modeling and anthology of connotations etc. respective to skills and traits, competencies and learning and the role of higher education. [26-41, 45-60, 102-103, 105-110, 114-138, 144-145, 147, 152]

Furthermore many studies were conducted in studying the employee efficiency and performance through various models in order to improve organizational performance. These models include ASTD Models for Human Performance Improvement based on Human Performance Technology [61], Emotional intelligence models [62-69], Spiritual intelligence models [70-71], Competency Mapping models [72-76], HRD Model [77], Self-efficacy and Learning Orientation model [78], Social Skills model [79], Innovation model [80], Employee engagement model [81], IPS-EQ model [82], Theory Z [83], and Theory of Accountability (Theory A) [84-87], Organizational creativity theory [88], Organizational culture Model [89], Performance management model [90], and TQM and organizational performance model [91-93], etc. However, in order to realize such theories in organizations, many training models are also developed [94-100], which had sole objective of improving the employability; enhance productivity and performance through improved efficiency.

A comprehensive and rich analysis in context of futuristic skill sets and skill stability, specifically for employment skills across industries and geographies is very nicely covered in ‘The Future of Jobs Report’, by World Economic Forum, ‘Employment, Skills and Workforce Strategy for the Fourth Industrial Revolution’, (January 2016). [5-7]

Indeed the exhaustive study in this report aptly uses the concept of skills stability to illustrate the degree to which, by the year 2020, particular occupations and job types are expected to require skills that have hitherto not been part of that occupation’s core skill set today. The report stimulates deeper thinking about how governments, businesses, educators, training providers, employers and workers can manage the transformative impact of disruptive changes due to 4th Industrial Revolution, through enhanced collaborative partnerships for employment, skills and education. [5-7]

A study by Indeed Inc. ‘Labor Market Outlook 2016’ suggests that there is an increasing gap between employer’s expectation and the employability skills of job seekers. The report suggests, perhaps this gap is fuelled by primarily two types of mismatch viz.: Skills mismatch and Interests misalignment or in other cases, by shortages in the population, owing to aging or migration. Furthermore, there is a growing level of difficulty in filling jobs; and almost one third of employers find that, talent skill gaps have a medium to high impact on their competitiveness, productivity and ability to serve their clients satisfactorily. [15, 16]

In a talent shortage survey, results published by Manpower group, indicate that the percentage difficulty of filling jobs in India has risen from 13 % to 61% over last 10 years. The report finds that Indian companies struggle to find suitable employees mostly in Accounting and Finance, IT staff,

Technicians, Engineers, Corporate management, Sales and Marketing, Buying and Procurement as well as Teaching and Research. The primary reasons found for such difficulty in filling job vacancies, encompass lack of technical competencies (hard skills), lack of appropriate experience, lack of workplace competencies (soft skills), demand of higher remuneration, over qualified applicants and undesirable geographic location, apart from company size and image. [15, 16]

According to India Skills Report'16, *(a comprehensive survey and analysis published jointly by CII, Wheebox, Association of Indian universities, People strong and LinkedIn)*, most of the top skill space required by employers was in 4 primary skill types: Domain Expertise (28%), Integrity values and result orientation (27%), Learning agility and interpersonal skills (18%), Numerical and Logical ability (9%). This was followed with Cultural Fitment (8%), Communication (6%) and Adaptability (4 %). However, the results of India Skill Report'17 shows emphasis tilting towards Communication up at 14 % in 2017. [13, 14]

4. RESEARCH METHODOLOGY / APPROACH AND LIMITATIONS:

Qualitative research is initially adopted to develop a theoretical conceptual framework of employability skill management quotient, with exploratory inputs from secondary data, published reports, literature review, group interviews, brain storming and jury of expert opinion, which has contributed to the consolidation of this concept. Quantitative and Empirical investigation of the ESMQ model concept for various collaborative engagement correlations, and linkages with skill trait quotients as well as skill elements is recommended and proposed in differential context for future in-depth understanding.

5. EMPLOYMENT AND EMPLOYABILITY:

Companies are demanding more and more in terms of skills and competencies from Management and Engineering Students graduating from Indian Universities and Colleges. [14, 18, 20, 28, 31, 35-38, 101-103]. To name a few, such as cognitive flexibility, critical thinking [104], aided with analytical, logical and mathematical reasoning, and task-activity-effort-result oriented resource management ability with a problem solving and negotiating attitude, enhanced with social and system wide decision making skills; or an out of box innovational creative human resource talent; that is perpetually self motivated and in a throughput enhancing motion towards the strategic goals of the organization. [6, 8, 12, 14, 31, 35-41, 76-78,105-110]

Knowledge, Skills, Ability and Attitude (KSAA) constitute the basic elements for professional development. Usually the term skills can mean to refer work-related capabilities of an employee to perform a job successfully. However, skills and ability may differ, wherein ability may refer to more fundamental and enduring attributes of an individual, such as physical or cognitive abilities that are formed over a longer period, often beginning in early childhood education. [Adopted from 5-7, 111]

- Knowledge- gained / learnt / experienced understanding of concepts.
- Skills- Proficiency developed through training, experience, practice and sustained effort to do something well repeatedly and produce results efficiently.
- Ability- physical or cognitive strengths formed over a longer period.
- Attitude- Predisposition manner to handle the circumstances and reaction to the same.
- "Aptitude" practically refers to an individual's ability to learn or adapt certain new skills. For instance, verbal, numerical or abstract reasoning for cognitive knowledge [112]

- Competencies-A measurable pattern of knowledge, skills, abilities, behaviors, and other characteristics that an individual needs to perform work roles or occupational functions successfully. (Behavioral, Functional, Professional, Technical etc.) [5-7, 72, 111,112]

Employability- Varying descriptions and perceptions on the term employability, from the employee and employer perspective and its contextual transformation, over the past four decades indicate the systemic and dynamic character of employability. To improve deeper understanding about employability, various research constructs, psycho-social correlates, models and linkages, as well as role and responsibility for employability development, have been well researched and recommended nicely. [29-60, 102-110]

In this context the paper presumes Employability as a summation of skills, abilities, knowledge, attitude, behavior, competencies and capabilities as skill traits, in a graduating student or a prospective employee, that enable individuals to get and retain employment, demonstrating value addition to the employer organization, efficiently & effectively; and competitively demonstrating a successful professional career in their respective macro dynamic environment.

In the education sector, the reference to skills may tend to lay emphasis on knowledge acquisition, assimilation and achievement of education outcome in terms of qualification and certification. On the other hand, businesses and industry lay emphasis on the practicality of acquired credentials in terms of capabilities or competencies expected from a graduate student, for a given functional job in an industry domain, as an employee that they may be able to use. [5-7]

Will it be right to assume that the Businesses and Industry have a nagging perception of overpromise and under delivery of value proposition from their academic value chain partners? Whether does it mean there were redundancies in academic value addition, due to education management, policy framework or regulatory stipulations? Or will it be appropriate to presume that contrary to the way the concepts and theories are taught in classroom factories; the graduating student needs a different education product mix, with a futuristic academic value proposition? [11, 12, 17-29, 41, 45, 50-52, 56, 58, 59, 101-103, 113]

A fresh perspective is therefore required supplementing the professional development efforts, and in order to overcome the widening gap in functional or occupational employability skills as well as the degree of productive professionalism sought by employers from graduating students, especially in emerging and developing economies. [85, 97, 120, 121]

6. ACADEMIA: INDUSTRY

Current Job Scenario in India is highly competitive and professionally demanding. Beyond class room learning, graduating engineers and management students have to multi-skill, multitask and train themselves with contemporary techniques for a professional career, in order to survive and succeed in any organization.

For instance in B2B (Business to Business Context), it's usually the engineering background managers, who do Techno Commercial dealings with Key customers from different backgrounds. Technology driven-Customer centric value engineering in products and services makes such jobs equally demanding and challenging. Engineers not only have to specialize onto their core technical discipline, but also have to actively engage with B2B buying centre members, understand B2B Buyer Procurement Process, interface with end to end clients and understand the delivery of benefits from the value engineering that they have produced in the factories. Additionally they have to demonstrate

in depth techno-commercial acumen, product and service application knowledge and awareness of domain trade practices.

Similarly across various professional jobs, organizations at the basic expect employees to demonstrate in depth industry awareness, business commercial acumen, technology awareness as well as leadership skills and interpersonal relationship smartness supplemented with emotional intelligence and maturity in order to work comfortably in teams.

Any Professional Education University needs to develop a deep sense of responsibility among youth and channelize their creative energies for a meaningful choice of profession. Moreover, it is imperative that this choice be aligned to the passion and potential of the Student.

Notwithstanding the unorganized and fragmented Training Industry, that is preoccupied with a huge incubation training demand to cater to businesses and industry, the education industry, must capitalize upon this golden opportunity in the knowledge economy, by increasing the 'academic value through-put' for its stake holders. While the focus is still to augment the employability of graduating students, Indian academia is gearing up and making tremendous efforts for competing globally through participation in policy reforms, improving academic environment and research productivity as well as invoking faculty accountability on building expertise from applied research.

A holistic knowledge enablement ecosystem, aided with an entrepreneurial perspective that fundamentally simulates functional capabilities and which is stimulated by hands-on experiential training for professional development may surely provide an outstanding academic experience to students. This is further supplemented with exposure to industry domain knowledge, adoption of new teaching and training tools, applied learning for practice of management concepts, practical training exposure to enhance functional skills consequently improving operational productivity of student managers and engineers. Yet indeed the supplementing of emotional maturity is being improved through soft skills and social grooming. Education focus is gradually shifting from text book loaded theoretical learning towards Applied Learning. Advantages of applied learning are inclusive of the benefits to influence innovation and entrepreneurship by enabling functional skills confidence. This effort requires a strong and ever-growing Industry and Academia partnership as a two way channel. [122-138]

The strengthening of links between universities and industry cannot be possible without introducing a common language. This 'common ground' would enable academics and business practitioners to develop mutually beneficial relationships. (Adopted from Amir Fazlagic. 2005) [113]

7. SYNTHESIZING THE CONCEPT

Engagements between Industry and Academia:

To develop capacity enhancing linkages between businesses, industry, training and education, a systematic as well as structured approach towards collaborative engagements are perceived keeping in mind the Industry Academia Interface (I.A.I.) and that can be looked from both aspects of industry and academia for value addition and value integration. [139-150]

See Figure 1 below

Figure 1: A graphical perspective value addition and value integration

C.O.D.E. = En-Code + De-Code [Resource and Knowledge Products]

Value Proposition:

En-CODE: From Campus to Corporate for Value Addition.

De-CODE: From Corporate to Campus for Value Integration

Collaborative engagement for Organization Development and Employability (CODE) includes four types of engagements that are classified as 1) Knowledge engagements, 2) Technology engagements, 3) Professional functional engagements, and 4) Socio-Cultural engagements. To illustrate representation of the four collaborative engagements, a graphical perspective is proposed below in figure 2.

Figure 2: A graphical perspective of Industry Academia Interface (I.A.I)

Approaches for C.O.D.E. methodology are categorized as resource based and knowledge based and described below in Figure 3

	Industry side Impact	Society side Impact	
Student Side Impact	Professionally Employable Human Resource	Qualified and Progressive Human Resource- Educational certifications	Resource based Products (En-Code)
Faculty Side Impact	Useful Knowledge for finding solutions to the problems of industry, businesses, and society	Offer solutions to the most pressing problems (may bring in the reality of future today)	Knowledge based Products (De-Code)

Figure 3: A quadrant of Resource based (En-Code) and Knowledge based (De-Code) view

Resource Based – Student Side Impact:

En-Code:

Redefining academic value proposition through applied learning and accelerated training to provide an experiential exposure for professional development of graduating students and improving their overall employability can be one approach; i.e. value addition beyond knowledge acquisition and qualification credentials, towards professionally employable human resource [PEHR]. [139-150]

In other words, to become a competitive green channel resource provider, rather than just producing, ‘Qualified Yet Not Employable workforce’. Here it can be referred to as producing a progressive, high on employability skills, professionalism, business maturity and technically smart, productive young Indian Executive: En-CODE

Co-relating the four collaborative engagements on the Student side, for their professional development, a simple conceptual four Quadrant Model of Employability Skill Management Quotient (ESMQ) is proposed with its following sub categories.

1. Intellectual Skill Management Quotient: ISMQ
2. Technical Skill Management Quotient: TSMQ
3. Professional or Functional Skill Management Quotient: PSMQ
4. Socio-cultural Skill Management Quotient: SCSMQ

On the lines of ‘The Future of Jobs Report’ [5-7], an attempt is made to manually reproduce and rename employability skill, mapping to collaborative engagements and combine them for inclusion into respective quotients. Moreover, for flexibility and adaptability, each sub-skill trait set, can be a group of elemental core work related skills, respective to a given function or domain.

A graphical representation of ESMQ is illustrated below.

Levels	Intellectual Skill	Technical Skills	Professional Skill	Socio-Cultural Skill
EMQ1	Conceptual Clarity	IT Computation skill assets	Functional/ Vocational capability	Soft skills, Emotional Intelligence and Social Etiquettes
EMQ2	Knowledge Application	Technical expertise in functional area	Professional Expertise and Productive result orientation	Socio-cultural responsibility, Ethics, Integrity and Leadership
EMQ3	Subject area Research	Technology integration and Management capabilities	Business and Economics maturity	Societal and Corporate Peer Networking,
EMQ4	Industry domain depth	Resource and operations optimization competence	Innovative and Entrepreneurial acumen	Community integration, Training and development

Figure 4: Essential elements of ESMQ Model. (Tabular)

ESMQ is proposed to be a non quantitative summation of varying elements of Skill respective to a given Function in a given Domain i.e. $ESMQ = \sum ISMQ_n + \sum TSMQ_n + \sum PSMQ_n + \sum SCSMQ_n$.

Figure 5: Essential elements of ESMQ Model. (Graphical)

Knowledge Based- Faculty Side Impact:

De-Code:

Co-relating the four collaborative engagements on the Faculty side for producing superior knowledge through applied research useful to businesses, industry and society, and which offers solutions that may bring in the reality of future today, could be another approach; i.e. value integration beyond academic asset for building intellectual capital with collaborative engagements for organizational development and sustainable growth of businesses, industry and society as a whole. [139-157]

From an intrinsic and extrinsic viewpoint of conceptualizing, creating, communicating, delivering and capturing the value of knowledge, expertise, skills, competencies and resources at academia; four Knowledge product lines are proposed for value integration between academia and industry. Here it may refer but not limiting to packaging knowledge and expertise from research, consulting, techno-management solutions and trainings to Businesses and Industry: De-CODE.

See Figure 6 Value Integration for De-Code Knowledge opportunity categories below.

Figure 6: Knowledge products categories illustrated as four vertical product lines (De-Code)

From Fig: 5 & 6 above: Combining Resource Based & Knowledge Based Components for the Industry Academia Interface (I.A.I.) See Figure 7 below

Figure 7- Industry Academia Interface (I.A.I.) mapped to C.O.D.E

The goal shall be to become a competitive and a collaborative value adding resource by harvesting and delivering value of knowledge and resources to industry and society, i.e. expanding the existing knowledge platform for a wider intellectual and resource spectrum. Per say with an aim to create productive synergies (value integration) between university and industry sectors, for a mutually profitable relationships that could be prepositioned as a multi lateral intellectual highway for the technology economy; from academia to industry and vice versa. [3, 8, 12, 21, 22, 42-44, 139, 140, 141, 142, 148-157]

8. ANALYSIS OF THE MODEL:

8.1 Advantages of the Model: ESMQ and CODE framework brings to refocus value engagements and linkages with Graduate employability and I.A.I. (University Industry Collaboration). The model builds a conceptual framework and connectivity in the contemporary perspective of the evolving university purpose i.e. of providing education and developing knowledge, vs. contributing to the professional, technological and socio economic wellbeing of the economy and citizens in today's knowledge economy. ESMQ as a resource based and CODE as Knowledge based, together build a mutually beneficial highway for academia and stakeholders.

8.2 Benefits of the Model: CODE Channelizes traditional academic effort towards capturing value of knowledge with effective and efficient resource based productivity. The concept suggests looking beyond tuition fees and donations etc, towards alternative sources of potential revenue, consequently reducing financial pressures on private low funded private universities i.e. knowledge creation to knowledge delivery and capturing its commercial value. Additional benefits would result into enhanced reputation, legitimacy, up-skilling, motivation and revitalized direction to traditional academic efforts. Whereas ESMQ model and levels are facilitative to designing professional development interventions for improving graduate employability through ALPs thus value adding to the core academic purpose.

8.3 Constraints of the Model: Commercialization threat if not clearly border-lined may affect the autonomous and independent nature of academic work and influence deviating from the fundamental university mission. Development of new skills, competencies and re-organization of structures, process flows and measures to evaluate workload would need appreciable re-engineering of curriculum and policies for strategic re-alignment within the existing environment. Sharing of resources, time frames, slow bureaucratic redundancies and administrative management may slow down the practical implementation, performance and realization of objectives. Conflict of interest, varying frame of reference, overstepping, agreements and contracts, disclosures and restrictions, dispute settlement require legal and regulatory support.

8.4 Disadvantage of the Model: Strengthening of the proposal by improving nomenclature not limiting to theoretical narrative aided with Quantitative and empirical correlations, experimentation of model and manual development for best practices is required. Notwithstanding in view of vastness of industry sector domains and job functions across businesses, requiring varying types of core work related skill sets at different career levels, the degree and intensity of skill units, within a subset group of skill trait, would need a very comprehensive focused and exhaustive research insight, domain sector wise.

9. CONCLUSION AND RECOMMENDATIONS:

An accelerated learning program (ALP) intervention for supplementing the professional development and grooming of students is based upon developing their overall Employability Skill. The purpose of such Accelerated Learning Programs (ALPs) should be to inculcate analytical and problem solving skills, with the help of team work, leadership development, sharing of fundamental perspectives, conceptual clarity, intellectual rigor and practical field work during the training sessions, gradually conducted in stages from EMQ1 to EMQ4.

"ALPs" should go beyond to polish the personality of young graduates and postgraduates to make them city smart in social etiquettes, manners, ethics, emotional maturity and social leadership, thus instilling Community Confidence, encompassing students of various Professional Courses. These endeavors should go beyond class room teaching and can be supplemented with periodic interventions through Accelerated Learning Programs (ALP's) designed using ESMQ and based upon professional development need assessment of students.

From the perspective of training need assessment, the classification proposed in ESMQ would be versatile for arriving at an appropriate loading of topic/subject/skill specific training methodology in order to design, develop, and deliver an accelerated skill enhancement intervention to a given target audience in a focused manner. ALPs should be designed to target common student cluster groups and enroll them through compulsory participation of ALP workshops that can be integrated into the academic curriculum or semester calendar as a 1, 2, 3 day workshops. This can be further supplemented with a "*Four Quadrant Assessment and Grading*" as a mandate for Graduate Qualification.

Emerging and upcoming universities should go beyond the boundaries of their own campuses, reach out to their stake holders, and thus carve a niche in high growth business verticals in India through applied Research, Training and Consulting for building their intellectual capital. These efforts will consequently assist organizations in efficiently engineering the knowledge syntheses, into processes and products for the benefit of stakeholders.

Endeavoring for Value creation, the internal challenges of implementation and seamless execution within institutions can be only overcome, if a cohesive team is formed that is highly motivated, committed and focused compassionately to the cause of ALPs. Moreover, a change management initiative would be needed to catalyze the motivation level of ALP team for achieving higher quality benchmarks.

For a synergetic integration of ALPs into curriculum, a partnership or bilateral mentorship from Industry to Academia and vice versa shall become a common forum for improvements and future alignment. Industry Mentor's central role will be vital to infuse energy through coaching and mentoring.

All the above multidirectional efforts endeavor to instill confidence into students and sharpen their skills. In nutshell, these efforts "*humbly focus upon cultivating Leaders and Responsible Corporate Citizens in their chosen Professions*"; so that they can face tougher career challenges in professional life, and eventually sustain their career growth on a long term employment journey, enabling them to come out as a winner.

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